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ЖУРНАЛ КУЛЬТУРА И ИСКУССТВО | JOURNAL OF CULTURE AND ART

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THE PROBLEM OF GENERATIONS IN THE NEW FILM BY K. KAMALOVA "ROAD TO NOWHERE".

ANNOTATION

This article provides information about Kamara Kamalova's film "Road to Nowhere," released a year ago. This material is part of a full-fledged film study of the director's creative path and filmography. This chapter provides the content and constructive analysis of the new film, which is completely different from previous works both in style and in mood. The material reflects personal position on the plot.

Key words: auteur cinema, film theory, director, genre, director's personality, drama, script, film studies.

ПРОБЛЕМА ПОКОЛЕНИЙ В НОВОМ ФИЛЬМЕ К.КАМАЛОВОЙ «ДОРОГА В НИКУДА». КОНСТРУКТИВНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье представлена информация о вышедшем год назад фильме Камары Камаловой «Дорога в никуда». Данный материал является частью полноценного исследования творческого пути и фильмографии режиссера. Приводится содержание и конструктивный анализ нового фильма, который совершенно отличается от предыдущих работ как по стилистике, так и по настроению. В материале отражена личная позиция к сюжету.

Ключевые слова: авторское кино, кинотеория, режиссёр, жанр, личность режиссера, драма, сценарий, киноведческое исследование.

QAMARA KAMOLOVA “KIM DEYA SENI” YANGI FILMINING XULOSA VA KONSTRUKTIV TAHLIL

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada Qamara Kamolovanning “Kim deya seni” filmi haqida ma’lumot berilgan. Ushbu maqola rejissyorning ijodiy yo’li va filmografiyasi to’g’risidagi to’liq tadqiqotining qismidir. Ushbu bobda rejissyorning yangi filmning xulosa va konstruktiv tahlili keltirilgan. Bu film avvalgi Q.Kamolovanning asarlardan uslubi va kayfiyati bilan butunlay farq qiladi. Maqola tadqiqotchining shaxsiy taassurotini keltiradi.

Kalit soʻzlar: muallif kinosi, kino nazariyasi, rejissyor, janr, rejissyor shaxsiyati, drama, ssenariy, kinoshunoslik, tadqiqot.

Famous Uzbek director with more than a half century filmography released last year a completely new film “Road to Nowhere” in Uzbek language called “Kim deya seni”, to reach our spiritual emptiness or give a fat zero for behavior.

The film was shot with the support of two studios - the private Buhoriylar and the state-owned Uzbekfilm. This fact is noteworthy because, according to the director, Uzbekfilm has always a hard time financing any projects, and while great creators and directors with an approved budget wait for several years, kind independent studios, such as Buhoriylar, always come to the rescue.

The author of the idea and script was Kamara Kamalova herself. Apparently, director is very concerned about our current generation and this is reflected very poignantly in her film. The level of nihilism and immorality in which Kamalova wrote the young, carefree unhelpful heroes produces a very depressing, gloomy impression.

We must give credit to the DOP cameraman and composition artist. The atmosphere of the city is conveyed perfectly. Exactly in the same commercial way as the fabulous eastern Buhara remembered by tourists all over the world. I just like Buhara so every landscape that reminds me this old ancient tale town warms my heart. Despite bad script.

This is so heartbreaking drama, which is very difficult to stand, to sit through an hour and a half without self-torture and facepalming. But the only thing that saves the movie is cameraman creativity and visual taste. The cozy interior and the warmth smoothness of the shot calms nervous eyes of the spectator.

Briefly speaking about the plot, this is a classic drama about the problem of fathers and sons, grannies and grandchildren/orphans, or maybe even a tragedy about irresponsible child. The main character is played by Malika Ibragimova, a famous theater actress in Uzbekistan.

And the second heroine is played by cameraman daughter Kamila Rasulmukhamedova. In the story, Malika practically plays herself. An orphan girl comes to rent a room in her luxurious Moroccan-style guest house. A relative or an acquaintance is not clear to us in the film and it doesn't matter. She gets along very well with this girl and they have a warm and friendly relationship. Along the way, the film develops flashbacks, where the main character, the mistress of the house, remembers her youth, her handsome husband, played by the famous Uzbek playboy Yigitali Mamajanov. He was an artist in his youth and left after death a huge inheritance - collection of paintings. Malika decorated walls of her oriental style home with this oil on canvas paintings.

Girl Lola (Kamola) and Gavhar (Malika) granny spend a lot of time together. The girl is trying to improve her life, works in a restaurant, meets with her friends from college. Malika tries to help her and encourages her to continue her studies, teaches her to play the dutar. The girl Lola meets a completely unfamiliar guy who gives her a ride to her workplace and takes her back.

This unknown young man deceives Lola, saying that he works in the cinema industry. He penetrates the trust of this naive young girlie so deeply that she brings him to meet Gavhar at her house. They arrange a tea party and in the process of communicating, talking with this young man, Gavhar realizes that he is an absolute swindler scoundler and a deceiver. He behaves very ugly and vulgar.

But Lolochka doesn't understand this. It was as if she had become blind or befuddled by the deceitfulness of this serpent. The ugliest Sad events unfold when a girl steals jewelry from Gavhar and, together with this guy, takes it to a pawnshop. After that guy takes all this money and disappears, previously promised her that he will get her a role in a movie...

The old woman, seeing that the jewelry is not there, immediately understands what is wrong and becomes terribly upset. Seeing her sad face, Lola goes back and looks for this crook guy. She finds his place of work, finds out that he doesn't actually work there, but is listed as a driver, then she somehow finds his apartment address, and when she comes to his home, she discovers his wife. As a result, she ends up with this swindler catching her on the road, raping and beating her. Heartbroken and pregnant, she goes back to granny's house and promises to return all the jewellery to her. Lola has nothing to do so she goes to cry her college friend, and yes of course he, too, has been in love with her for a long time and is ready to forgive all her mistakes.

This college boy even ready to become father of her unborn child from scoundler. After the drama scene in the rain, she takes her friend into her room at Gavhars house and wipes him with a towel to dry him after the rain. Here comes very unpleasant misunderstanding situation: Gavhar enters the room... Again, Lolochka spilled oil... Again, Lolochka looks like easy little whore behind granny's eyes. Losing her rage, Gavhar says to Lola "Get out". The girl and the guy go to his house. And in the end, this guy introduces her to his parents as his future bride.

This college boy's parents don't like this idea. They reject Lola. After this young people have an explanation scene, where Lola, out of resentment, mutually rejects him and runs away from him. Although, it could be like, "happiness" in the end: "Humble yourself and arrange your life, Lola!" But Lola refuses everything...

Next, we see the final episode, Gavhar walks through the narrow streets of Buhara. She tries to find her dog, she feels bad. As in the classic Godfather the scene with a slice of tangerine in his hands, our Godmother gets her heart attack. She sits down on the bench, as if transported into parallel space. Finally, Lola runs to Gavhar's house and finds her lying with polaroid pictures of her youth. The film ends on this confusing note. With an open ending, a huge pile of problems and logical questions for both heroines the girl and the granny.

The theme of intergenerational relationships is directly related to the motif of time and the author's concepts of historical development. It remains relevant throughout the history of literature. A comparison of generations of heroes is contained already at the beginning of Homer's Iliad [1]. The clash of old and new, ethical ideals of different eras, behavioral norms of "fathers" and "sons" drives the plot of "Antigone" by Sophocles and "King Lear" by W. Shakespeare. It is inherent in the very nature of the comedy genre, which "... goes back to the rural holidays of the Attic village" [2], is born from the cult of fertility, the change of winter in spring, the old with the new, which is naturally manifested in many literary monuments of Aristophanes, Terence, and Shakespeare.

Screenshots from the movie "Road to Nowhere" by K.Kamalova.

The interpretation of this topic is closely related to paradigm that predetermined the cultural and historical context in which the conflict between fathers and sons unfolds at every stage of history. Based on the fundamental changes in the criteria and images of the artistic, its nature, goals, place in society, the relationship between the author and the addressee at the turn of the 18th–19th centuries, when “normative artistry” was replaced by “aesthetic creativity,” we easily discover how this “tectonic shift” is reflected in the principles of reflecting generational conflict [3].

From the one point the plot of Kamalova’s movie is very ordinary: the problem of generations, youthful maximalism, the difficult relationship between grandmother and granddaughter.

But the degree of closeness between them is completely incomprehensible to the viewer. Even if we know from the titles that the girl is orphan, her friendship with old woman is very kind and household. As a result, interpersonal line of relations between an adult and a teenager is completely erased. And, the main point of script is that the story was filmed in the form of a parable tale. Because if it is not so and we analyse it as some kind of real drama, - more serious story, then all the tragicomedy nature of the plot would turn into a crime. Gavhar would have no choice but to hand over guest strangers (Lola and her scoundrel) to the internal police department.

We have two main characters here; it is hard to say which one is the secondary one. As if there were two main plots, two storylines. The line of granny, old loneliness and flashbacks to sweet memories with her husband. Another line about orphan young girl, and her generally absolutely irresponsible acting character, completely disgusting behavior from the point of morality, of any ethics values at all.

It is necessary to decide whether there is a separate “grandmother archetype.” There is no specific “grandmother” archetype in the works of the famous scientist Jung. The researcher will only find the “Old Woman” archetype or the “Witch” archetype. The “Granny” archetype developed in the 20th century, primarily in Eastern Europe. A grandmother can only be understood in tandem with her grandson or granddaughter. This is “grandmother and granddaughter”, “grandmother reads a bedtime story to the children”. “grandmother passes on the secrets of home economics to her granddaughter.” Of course, the most famous fairytale type of grandmother is the grandmother from fairy tale “Little Red Riding Hood”. The grandmother lives in a secluded house in the forest, and her granddaughter brings her pies and along the way finds herself in an unpleasant situation known to every schoolchild. For our contemporary, a grandmother is something strictly functional (useful, bright) and at the same time something deeply mystical and irrational [4].

Therefore, if you wonder what the director and scriptwriter want to say here, you come to conclusion that apparently the author of this movie does not have very positive impressions of our young generation. There is no soulful Granny archetype position in here. Apparently, experienced in life creator - of the script is very disappointed, about us. The way how director describes this main young heroine Lola as the personification of immorality, brings us to a sad reflection. What if this girl would be her real granddaughter? What kind of premise, super idea or message from the author is hidden here? What should we do? What should we change in our life? Why there so many lies, cunning, sin and mistakes? I don’t know. You can take this movie as a parable, or as a crooked otherworldly mirror, some disgusting image. Because it is impossible to watch this film seriously. This is very unpleasant.

We must pay tribute to Malika Ibragimova and her impersonating character. She is like the only light and standing ethics in the plot. The image of an intelligent, sophisticated alone old woman that she created in this movie completely distinguishes her from the typical Uzbek corpulent makhalla kainashki who are regulars at banquet halls and TV shows “Olovli Kelin”. Completely alone, abandoned by everyone, with pain and sadness and powerlessness, she eventually frees herself, letting everything go by itself and leaving this life.

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